

Potentiometric Determination of Protonation Constant of 4,5-Dimethyl-2-Hydroxy Acetophenone and its Oxime[‡]

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Protonation constant of 4,5-dimethyl-2-hydroxy acetophenone and its oxime has been determined in aqueous-dioxane [20 to 75% (v/v)] at different ionic strengths (0.01M to 0.1M NaClO₄) and temperatures 20°, 30° & 40° potentiometrically. The value of change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been calculated. The value of pK_m^H (minimum pK_1^H value at θ°) has been calculated from Harned's equation.

O-HYDROXY acetophenones and their oximes are very interesting reagents in respect of their complexing property. These ligands have been shown to be useful reagents for spectrophotometric and gravimetric estimations of a number of the transition metals¹⁻⁴. However, relatively few studies of their chelating properties have been reported⁵⁻⁹. The systematic study of the chelating properties of the disubstituted 2-hydroxy acetophenones and their oximes have been undertaken in this laboratory⁹. In the present communication, the protonation constant of 4,5-dimethyl-2-hydroxy acetophenone (DMHA) and its oxime (DMHAO) have been calculated in aqueous-dioxane medium at different ionic strengths (μ) and temperatures by the method of Irving and Rossotti¹⁰. Thermodynamic functions and pK_m^H (minimum pK_1^H value at θ°) have been calculated. The effect of the change in dielectric constant, temperature and on pK_1^H value has also been studied.

Experimental

Reagents and Apparatus :

The ligands were prepared as described earlier¹¹. Solutions of sodium hydroxide and perchloric acid B.D.H. (AnalaR) were prepared and standardized as usual. Sodium perchlorate (Reidel) was used to maintain the desired ionic strength. Dioxane was purified by the method described by Vogel¹². An inert atmosphere was maintained by bubbling nitrogen through the solution.

The pH measurements were made with systronic digital pH meter type 335 with a sensitivity of 0.01 unit. The pH meter was calibrated at pH 4.05 and 9.18 with aqueous potassium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffers respectively.

In aqua-dioxane mixtures the pH values were corrected by the use of Van-Uitert and Hass equation¹³⁻¹⁶.

$$-\text{Log} [H^+] = B + \log U_H$$

where $B = \text{pH}$ meter reading and U_H conversion factor. The conversion factor was obtained from the difference between the 'B' and the theoretical value $-\log [H^+]$.

The value of $\log U_H$ at a fixed temperature can be obtained for any ionic strength from the expression :

$$\text{Log } U_H = \log U_H^0 + \log \gamma_{\pm}$$

where γ_{\pm} is the activity coefficient and $\log U_H^0$ is the correction at zero ionic strength in the solvent under study.

Procedure :

The experimental procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹⁰ was used for potentiometric titrations of the following thermostated solutions in nitrogen atmosphere :

- (i) : 2.0 ml HClO₄ (0.05 M),
- (ii) : (i) + 5.0 ml ligand (0.01 M)

against standard carbonate free sodium hydroxide (0.05 M). The ionic strengths, 0.1 M, 0.05 M and 0.01 M were maintained by the addition of appropriate sodium perchlorate solutions and keeping the total volume at 40.0 ml. Such titrations were carried out in different dioxane-water mixtures.

Calculations :

The Irving and Rossotti's method¹⁰ was used for the calculations of \bar{n}_H (average number of

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TABLE 1—Log K_1^H VALUES FOR DMHA AND DMHAO IN DIOXANE-WATER SYSTEM AT $30 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$

Ligand	Dioxane-Water% (v/v), $\mu = 0.1M$					Dioxane-Water 75% (v/v) Ionic Strength (M)		
	0*	20	40	60	75	0.05	0.01	0.00**
DMHA	9.60	9.93	10.42	11.35	12.18	12.36	12.53	12.70
DMHAO	8.20	8.57	9.05	9.94	10.76	10.87	11.12	11.30

* By Extrapolation to zero percentage Dioxane.

** By Extrapolation to zero Ionic strength.

protons associated with the ligand) from the titration curves. The pK_1^H was obtained from the formation curve between \bar{n}_H and pH , at $\bar{n}_H = 0.5$. The value was also calculated using pointwise calculation method and least square method. The values obtained from different methods were in good agreement. The average value of pK_1^H in various percentage (v/v) of dioxane and different ionic strengths are reported in Table 1.

The experimental accuracy of the protonation constant values can be verified by comparing the values of \bar{n}_H found experimentally and those of calculated from the equation :

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{\sum \beta_i [H^+]^i}{1 + \sum \beta_i [H^+]^i}$$

The difference between \bar{n}_H (exp.) and \bar{n}_H (cal.) is found to be smaller than 10% in most of the cases.

Results and Discussion

The introduction of a methyl group at any position in benzene ring results in weakening the acid strength of *o*-hydroxy acetophenone (HA). This is due to the electron releasing nature of the methyl group. The methyl group effect on pK_1^H value of HA due to :

- (i) Induction effect of methyl group.
- (ii) Increase intramolecular hydrogen bonding between hydrogen of phenolic -OH and oxygen of C=O group^{17,18}.
- (iii) Degree of solvation of ligand in solution.

The pK value of HA (11.85) was obtained in 75% dioxane at 30° and ionic strength $0.1M$ (NaClO_4) by Kamat and Dator⁶. In the present case the value is 12.18, the higher value is due to the substitution of $-\text{CH}_3$ groups but above said effects are smaller due to enlarged distance over which it has to operate.

It is interesting to examine the influence of substitution of an oximino group for a keto-oxygen. Comparison of the pK value of corresponding

ketone and keto-oxime shows that in all the cases studied the oxime has been found to be a stronger acid than ketone. This may be due to the intramolecular hydrogen bond present in the system as under :

(i) The O—H...N bond that may be expected to be present in the neutral oxime molecule is weaker than the O—H...O bond of the corresponding ketone. Consequently the release of phenolic hydrogen of the oxime is facilitated.

(ii) Another acid strengthening factor is the additional stability of the oxime anion due to the possibility of hydrogen bond formation by oxygen of phenolic group and hydrogen of oximino group.

Therefore, the pK value of DMHAO was found lower i.e. 10.76.

Effect of Varying Dielectric Constant :

With the dissociation of an acid the number of ions in solution increases. The degree of dissociation of acid depends on the dielectric constant (ϵ) of the medium. A solvent of low dielectric increases the electrostatic force between the ions and facilitate the formation of molecular species resulting in an increase pK value¹⁹ (Table I). The dielectric constant decreases with increase in dioxane percentage²⁰.

The change in pK_1^H with mole fraction of dioxane (n_2) is considered for the ligands under study. It gives a linear curve obeying the straight line relationship : $pK_1^H = mn_2 + C$, where m and C are slope of the line and intercept (pK_1^H at 0.0% dioxane) respectively. The values of m and C are 7 and 9.6 for DMHA and 9.7 and 8.2 for DMHAO respectively. The pK_1^H do not vary linearly with the reciprocal of ϵ of the medium at high percentage of dioxane.

Effect of Ionic Strength :

According to Huckel²² the interaction of the ions decrease with the increase in the μ of the medium in which the reactions are studied. Thus on increasing the μ of the medium the protonation constant decreases.

TABLE 2—DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND ΔH CALCULATED FROM HARNED'S EQUATION FOR DMHA AND DMHAO AT μ=0.10 M(NaClO₄)

Temp. (°K)	pK ₁ ^H (average)	pK _m ^H	-ΔG (K cal mole ⁻¹)	-ΔH (K cal mole ⁻¹) (average)	ΔS (Cal deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹)	-ΔH* (K cal mole ⁻¹)
DMHA						
293	12.35		16.58		29.27	7.75
303	12.18	10.45	16.91	8.01	29.39	7.87
313	11.97		17.17		29.27	7.95
DMHAO						
293	10.97		14.73		23.07	7.95
303	10.76	8.89	14.94	7.97	23.01	8.08
313	10.59		15.19		23.07	8.17

* ΔH Using Harned's Equation.

The formation curves (\bar{n}_H vs pH) were drawn at different μ . There was no change in the shape of the curves, suggesting the various species coexist in solution. The pK_1^H value also decrease with increase in the value of μ . Thermodynamic protonation constant were obtained by extrapolation the values of $\log K_1^H$ to zero ionic strength from the graph between $\log K_1^H$ vs $\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

Effect of Varying Temperature :

The temperature of the titration vessel was changed to the desired temperature and pH of the solution was noted on addition of NaOH.

The ionization constant of a weak acid is a function of temperature and generally it has a maximum value near room temperature. An examination of the data given in Table 2 reveals that pK_1^H value of the ligands decreases as the temperature is raised. The thermodynamic values such as free energy change (-ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for the ionization of ligands in 75% (V/V) dioxane water medium are calculated using the usual expressions :

$$\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K$$

$$\Delta H = 2.303R \frac{T_2 \cdot T_1}{T_2 - T_1} \log \frac{K''}{K'}$$

$$\Delta S = 2.303 R \log K + \frac{\Delta H}{T}$$

where $\log K''$ and $\log K'$ are the protonation constants at the absolute temperature T_2 and T_1 respectively.

The value of pK_m^H (minimum pK_1^H value at θ^0) was calculated by Harned's equation :

$$pK_1^H - pK_m^H = C (t - \theta)^2$$

where C = constant (5.0×10^{-5} degree⁻²) on rearrangement.

$$(pK_1^H - Ct^2) = -2C\theta t + (pK_m^H + C\theta^2)$$

Thus the plot of $(pK_1^H - Ct^2)$ vs t should be straight line with a slope of $-2C\theta$ and intercept $(pK_m^H + C\theta^2)$. The value of $pK_1^H - Ct^2$ for the ligands were plotted against temperature and it was observed that the plot is linear from this plot, the value of θ and pK_m^H were obtained and reported in Table 2. The plot pK_1^H Vs temperature is also linear. It has been observed by Harries and Wright^{2,4} that this temperature range is so far removed from the plot of pK_1^H vs temperature and is the linear portion of the parabola^{2,4}.

The value of ΔH was also calculated by Harned's^{2,3} equation :

$$\Delta H = 2.303 RT^2 (t - \theta) \times 10^{-4}$$

and are reported in Table 2.

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References

1. S. N. PODDAR, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1957, **154**, 254 ; 1957, **155**, 327.
2. H. SINGH and K. C. SHARMA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, **28**, 43.
3. M. H. GANDHI and M. N. DESAI, *Analyt. Chem. Acta*, 1968, **43**, 338.
4. K. LAL and S. P. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 973 ; *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 178.
5. L. B. MAGNUSSON, C. POSTMUS JR. and G. A. CRAIG, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 1711.
6. P. V. KAMAT and M. G. DATOR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 409 ; 1972, **49**, 261.
7. C. B. PATIL and R. P. PATIL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 312.
8. V. SESHAGIRI and S. BRAHMAJI RAO, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 353.
9. K. LAL, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut University, Meerut, 1976.

10. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397 ; 1954, 2904.
11. (Mrs). M. MITTAL, K. LAL and S. P. GUPTA, *Metals & Min. Review*, 1978 (accepted).
12. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green & Co., London, 1956, 177.
13. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. G. HASS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
14. I. D. CHAWLA and C. R. SPILLERT, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 2717.
15. B. RAO and H. B. MATHUR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 3919.
16. K. LAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17A**, 314 ; *Talanta*, 1979, **26**, 1171.
17. R. P. PATEL and R. D. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 2591.
18. L. N. FERGUSON, "The Modern Structural Theory of Organic Chemistry", Printice Hall, New Delhi, 1969.
19. M. GIULIO, "Electro Chemistry, Principles, Practices and Applications", Elsevier Amsterdam, 1963, 80.
20. A. J. GEMANT, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1942, **10**, 723.
21. H. S. HARNED and B. B. OWEN, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", Reinhold, New York, 1958, 113.
22. E. HUCKEL, *Physik Z.*, 1925, **26**, 93.
23. H. S. HARNED and L. KAZANJIAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **58**, 1912.
24. H. J. HARRIES and G. WRIGHT, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem* 1969, **31**, 3149.